

Spectral studies on some diethyl 2,3-dioxopentanedioate-2-arylhydrazones

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The newly prepared diethyl 2,3-dioxopentanedioate-2-arylhydrazones exist predominantly in the keto-hydrazone form stabilized by hydrogen-bonding between NH and ketonic CO resulting in a six-membered ring system. Effects of substituents and solvents on the charge transfer electronic band have been studied. Transition energy, oscillator strength and ionization potential values are reported.

3-Oxopentanedioic acid¹ and its diethyl ester derivatives² possess different biological activities. Also, hydrazo and azo compounds possess various biological activities³. A search through literature revealed that not much work has been done on the structural chemistry of diethyl 2,3-dioxopentanedioate-2-arylhydrazones (1)⁴. It has been shown⁵ that diethyl 2,3-dioxopentanedioate-2-phenylhydrazone exists predominantly in the azo-enolic form. The present article deals with the use of ir, nmr, electronic and mass spectroscopy to elucidate the structure of a series of coupling products of aryldiazonium salts with diethyl 3-oxopentanedioate.

X = a *o*-OH, b *p*-OH, c *p*-OCH₃, d *p*-CH₃,
e *p*-Br, f *p*-Cl, g *o*-COOH, h *o*-COOCH₃,
i *o*-NO₂, j *p*-NO₂

Results and Discussion

Diethyl 3-oxopentanedioate (DOPD) can exist in two tautomeric forms, keto and enol. The appearance of a broad medium band at 3450 cm⁻¹ supports the presence of enolic OH group which can be further supported by the existence of the OH deformation band at 1325 cm⁻¹, ν_{C=C} vibrational mode at 1650 and 1630 cm⁻¹, the CH deformation band of the enolic mode at 1440 cm⁻¹, and that of active methylene bending band at 1400 cm⁻¹⁶. All carbonyl groups show a strong broad band in the range 1700–1755 cm⁻¹.

Regarding the arylhydrazone derivatives, the appearance of a band at 3196–3112 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to the NH stretching mode. Compounds 1a, 1b and 1g exhibit a

Scheme 1. Possible tautomeric structures of diethyl-2,3-dioxopentanedioate-2-arylhydrazones.

broad band in the NH absorption region due to the stretching OH vibration of the substituents on the phenyl moiety. Absorption at 1609–1583 cm⁻¹ could be attributed to the conjugated C=N which is in good agreement with the reported results⁷. The absence of the azo absorption band at 1530 cm⁻¹ emphasizes the hydrazone structure A, B or C rather than the azo form (D) (Scheme 1). The ν_{C-N} conjugation band with the aryl group appears at 1328–1304 cm⁻¹⁸. The carbonyl groups of compounds 1a-j display two or three stretching bands. The lower frequency bands at ca 1698 and/or 1665 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to both ketonic and ester carbonyls which are conjugated with C=N and intramolecularly hydrogen bonded with the NH moiety⁹. On the other hand, the ν_{C=O} band of the other ester group appears at 1730 cm⁻¹ as that of (DOPD). The disappearance of ν_{OH} at 3450, δ_{OH} at 1325, ν_{C=C} at 1650, 1630 and δ_{OH} enolic at 1440 cm⁻¹ of (DOPD) from the spectra of compounds 1a-j excludes the enol form A. Moreover, the presence of CH stretching band of -CH₂CO- moiety of 1a-j at ca 1400 cm⁻¹ is in accordance with the keto forms B and

C. From the above discussion, the absence of the enol form may be interpreted by preferable H-bonding with ketonic C=O (form C) rather than the ester C=O (form B) which has been confirmed by other spectral data.

The ^1H nmr spectra exhibit signals at δ 2.4–2.6 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.20 (6H, t, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$) and 4.10 (4H, q, $2 \times \text{CH}_2$). Since the two ester moieties of compounds **1a–j** are not magnetically degenerate, the two ethyl groups give two adjacent triplets at δ 1.00–1.30 and two quartets at δ 3.95–4.35. A singlet at δ 3.65–3.95 corresponds to the active methylene group¹⁰ which appears at δ 3.65 in (DOPD). A multiplet signal observed at δ 6.75–8.20 is due to the spin-spin coupling of the aromatic protons. Compounds **1a–g** and **1j** exhibit a sharp NH signal at δ 11.75–13.89¹¹ which disappears on addition of D_2O , while NH signals of **1h** and **1i** overlap with the aromatic signals which have been confirmed from the integral curves. Compounds **1c** and **1d** have an additional singlet at δ 3.56 and 2.20 due to the methoxy and methyl protons¹¹ respectively. Compound **1h** shows singlet at δ 3.70 for the methyl ester group in the aryl moiety. A singlet at δ 9.30 for **1b** can be assigned to OH proton and that at δ 3.40 for **1g** can be assigned to COOH proton which disappears on addition of D_2O .

Based on the ir and ^1H nmr data, the coupling products **1a–j** exist predominantly in the keto-hydrazo form stabilized by a hydrogen bonding between NH and the ketonic CO resulting in a stable six-membered ring system.

The electronic absorption spectra (ethanol) of **1a–j** display mainly three absorption bands, and those of **1g**, **1h** and **1i** show four absorption bands, while **1i** exhibits an additional band. The first band at 201–206 nm may be as-

Fig. 1 Relation between Hammett substitution constant (σ_x) and (—) λ_{max} (nm) and (---) E_{ev} of C.T. band of diethyl α -arylhydrazones acetonedicarboxylate in ethanol

signed to the medium energy $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of the phenyl moiety ($^1L_a-^1A$)¹² which is supported by the ϵ values of $0.82-1.82 \times 10^4$. The second band observed at 240–250 nm has been attributed to the low energy $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of the phenyl moiety ($^1L_b-^1A$), which is evidenced by their ϵ values $0.82-1.43 \times 10^4$. The spectrum of **1i** shows this band at 275 nm. The third band at 361–391 nm may be assigned to the $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of the conjugated π -system influenced by intramolecular charge transfer (C.T.). The position of this band provides an additional evidence that compounds **1a–j** are in the hydrazo rather than in the azo form¹³. The fourth band at 222–226 nm may be attributed to $\pi-\pi^*$ transition within the hydrogen chelate ring formed by hydrazono-hydrogen atom and oxygen of the *ortho*-substituted group. The spectra of **1i** and **1j** show an additional band at 330 and 231 nm assigned to the electronic transition of the phenyl ring interacting with the nitro group¹⁴. The plots of λ_{max} of the C.T. band in ethanol against the Hammett substitution constant (σ)¹⁵ (Fig.1) show two linear parts intersecting at the unsubstituted compound, indicating that the position of the C.T. band is affected to some extent by the nature of the substituents. The red-shift associated with the λ_{max} of the C.T. band decreases as the

Fig. 2. Effect of solvent on the C.T. band of diethyl α -arylhydrazones acetonedicarboxylate

electron-donating property of the substituent decreases. On the other hand, for electron-withdrawing substituent the red-shift increases which may be attributed to increasing C.T. in the reverse direction. The spectra of compounds **1b–j** in various organic solvents show a weak solvent shift for the C.T. transition band. Such behavior is similar to that of the typical hydrazones¹⁶. The application of the Gati and Szalay equation¹⁷ as well as the dielectric functions given by Suppan¹⁸ gives linear relationship between ν_{max} and the dielectric constant functions ($D-1/D+1$, $f(D)$, $\Phi(D)$), showing that the dielectric constant is the main controlling factor in solvent shifts (Fig. 2). The values of the observed

transition energy (E_{obs}) and oscillator strength (f_{obs}) (Table 1) were calculated for compounds **1a-j** from their electronic spectra using the relation¹⁹,

$$I_p = a + bv_0$$

where I_p is the ionization potential, v_0 the energy of HOMO-LUMO $\pi-\pi^*$ transition and a and b are constants amounting to 5.11 and 0.701 respectively²⁰.

Table 1. Transition energy (E), oscillator strength (F) and ionization potential (I_p^*) of diethyl-2,3-dioxopentanedioate-2-arylhydrazones derivatives (**1a-j**)

Compd. no.	E_{obs} eV	$f_{\text{obs}} \times 10^{-8}$	I_p^* eV	Compd. no.	E_{obs} eV	$f_{\text{obs}} \times 10^{-8}$	I_p^* eV
1a	3.20	0.41	7.35	1f	3.44	0.43	7.52
	5.06	0.17	8.66		5.17	0.23	8.73
	6.12	0.27	9.40		6.16	0.23	9.43
b	3.18	0.49	7.34	g	3.40	0.48	7.49
	4.93	0.22	8.57		4.96	0.23	8.59
	6.17	0.19	9.44		5.58	0.22	9.02
c	3.22	0.63	7.37	h	3.44	0.54	7.52
	4.97	0.29	8.59		5.00	0.23	8.62
	6.18	0.22	9.44		5.50	0.28	8.97
d	3.38	0.43	7.48	i	3.22	0.29	7.37
	4.08	0.22	8.67		3.76	0.24	7.75
	6.15	0.21	9.42		4.50	0.19	8.26
e	3.43	0.40	7.51	j	3.33	0.47	7.44
	5.15	0.21	8.72		5.38	0.17	8.88
	6.15	0.22	9.42		6.15	0.16	9.42

* $a = 5.11, b = 0.701$.

The fragmentation patterns of the compounds are more or less the same with a high relative abundance of the molecular ion peak at m/z 322, 336, 320, 384, 340, 350,

Scheme 2

364, 351 and 351 for **1a-j** respectively. Most of the compounds show fragment peak due to the cleavage at the C-C bonds through path-A leading to fragment peak corresponding to $[\text{Ar-NH-N}\equiv\text{C}]^+$ which can also be obtained through path-B (Scheme 2). On further fragmentation of the latter by losing HCN it gives fragment peak corresponding to $[\text{N-Ar}]^+$. Another path of fragmentation, path-C, includes cyclization through loss of ethanol forming substituted pyridazinones¹² which gives $[\text{N-Ar}]^+$ on further fragmentation. Fragment $[\text{N-Ar}]^+$ of compounds **1a-d** and **1f** eliminates CN^\bullet and N^\bullet giving peaks corresponding to $[\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{X}]^+$ and $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{X}]^+$ respectively. Compounds **1a** and **1b** undergo further fragmentation to give m/z 52 and 65 corresponding to $[\text{C}_4\text{H}_4]^+$ and $[\text{C}_5\text{H}_5]^+$ respectively. Compound **1c** shows a fragment ion $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5]^+$ formed by rearrangement of the fragment ion m/z 107 with elimination of CH_2O . In compound **1d** the fragment ion $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3]^+$ m/z 91 forms tropylium ion²¹ which undergoes further fragmentation to give $[\text{C}_5\text{H}_5]^+$ m/z 65 and $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5]^+$ m/z 77. Compound **1f** gives its final fragments at m/z 75 and 63 corresponding to $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_3]^+$ and $[\text{C}_5\text{H}_3]^+$ respectively. Compounds **1g** and **1h** have their base peaks through such pyridazinone structure. The appearance of the fragment at m/z 115 for compounds **1e**, **1i** and **1j** assigned to $[\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OOCCH}_2\text{CO}]^+$ indicates that these compounds do not follow the cyclization mechanism. Compound **1i** loses its nitro group first, while compounds **1e** and **1i** give fragment ions at m/z 340 and 306 respectively, due to loss of $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{O}^\bullet$ radical.

Experimental

An ice-cold solution of diethyl 3-oxopentanedioate (DOPD; 5 mmol) in ethanol (200 ml) containing sodium acetate (35 g) was treated gradually with an equimolar amount of appropriately diazotized aromatic amine. The solution was kept for 1 h at 0–5°, then water was added. The resulting solids were crystallized from the appropriate solvents: **1a**, m.p. 139° (EtOH); **b**, 152° (MeOH); **c**, 60° (pet. ether); **d**, 80° (EtOH); **e**, 90° (pet. ether); **f**, 79° (pet. ether); **g**, 144° (MeOH); **h**, 89° (EtOH); **i**, 125° (EtOH); **j**, 108° (EtOH). M.p.s. of **1d**, **1g** and **1j** are in accordance ($\pm 1^\circ$) with those reported²². The phenyl derivative could not be prepared in pure state²². All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

IR spectra were obtained on a Pye-Unicam SP 3-300 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO- d_6) on a Varian EM 390 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard, electronic spectra on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 3B spectrophotometer and mass spectra on a GC MS-QP 1000 EX Shimadzu EI 70 eV instrument.

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